

The Impact of Industry 4.0 on Business Functions: A Research of Business Managers

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Abstract

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Industry 4.0,
Strategic
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Business

Industry 4.0 has changed all processes and business methods. Nowadays, the idea of Industry 4.0 is a strategy tool for businesses to be competitive. This study aims to ascertain the perspectives of business managers in one of the top firms within the building products sector regarding Industry 4.0. To do this, semi-structured interviews with participants were conducted utilizing questions chosen from the literature, and data were gathered as a result. A total of 13 business managers participated in the study. Content analysis method was used in the research. The research has shown that employees have positive and negative thoughts about industry 4.0 activities. However, it is often emphasized that industry 4.0 processes will bring advantages to businesses in the fields of human resources, management, production, marketing and public relations.

Endüstri 4.0'ın İşletme Fonksiyonları Üzerindeki Etkisi: İşletme Yöneticileri Üzerine Bir Araştırma

Özet

Keywords:

Endüstri 4.0,
Stratejik Yönetim,
İşletme
Fonksiyonları,
İşletme

Endüstri 4.0 tüm süreçleri ve iş yapış şekillerini değiştirmiştir. Günümüzde Endüstri 4.0 fikri işletmelerin rekabetçi olabilmesi için bir strateji aracıdır. Bu çalışma, yapı ürünleri sektörünün önde gelen işletmelerinin birinde yer alan işletme yöneticilerinin Endüstri 4.0'a ilişkin bakış açılarını tespit etmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bunun için literatürden seçilen sorular kullanılarak katılımcılarla yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler yapılmış ve bunun sonucunda veriler toplanmıştır. Araştırmaya toplam 13 işletme yöneticisi katılmıştır. Araştırmada içerik analizi yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Araştırma, çalışanların Endüstri 4.0 faaliyetlerine ilişkin olumlu ve olumsuz düşüncelere sahip olduğunu ortaya koymuştur. Bununla birlikte endüstri 4.0 süreçlerinin işletmelere insan kaynakları, yönetim, üretim, pazarlama ve halkla ilişkiler alanlarında avantajlar getireceği sıklıkla vurgulanmıştır.

INTRODUCTION

The expression "Industry 4.0" is a powerful instrument that is pervasive throughout the world and affects every facet of modern life. The phenomenon of Industry 4.0 has changed and transformed business activities. In this context, Industry 4.0 has brought about revolutions that have altered personnel qualifications and work content. In this setting, it becomes increasingly important for businesses to incorporate technologies that are age-appropriate in all of their operations, from marketing, accounting, and human resources to logistics and production systems (Yıldız, 2018: 548). Employees' ability to adapt to this new process and industry 4.0 awareness are important for the efficiency of businesses. It is important to determine employees' perceptions of Industry 4.0 in this new process. Because this new process will bring destructive changes in businesses. This kind of situation may negatively affect employees' motivation issues and productivity at work. Managers must manage this process effectively. In this context, talent management behaviors should be improved in employees and their adaptation to the process should be ensured.

This study aims to ascertain the perspectives of business managers in one of the top firms within the building products sector regarding Industry 4.0. In order to do this, participants were interviewed in a semi-structured manner using questions chosen from the literature, and data were gathered as a result. One approach of qualitative analysis used to develop the study's results was content analysis design. As part of the survey, find out what the employees think about the idea of Industry 4.0. The opinions of workers in the domains of production, public relations, marketing, human resources, and management were examined in this context.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resources

Organizations in the human resources sector have several new opportunities as a result of Industry 4.0. It has an overall effect on the increase of labor productivity, the development of human resources, the possibility of starting new industries, and the transfer of certain activities from humans to machines and robots (Adamková, 2020: 1). The responsibilities that employees play in terms of their health, personal lives, and working hours will be impacted by Industry 4.0 (Bulte, 2018: 3). Smart working and innovative digital production are examples of how Industry 4.0 is altering the time and place of work. More diversified and flexible forms (in terms of work time and space) will likely replace the traditional 9-5 job schedule (Bissola & Imperatori, 2020: xv). Consequently, firms' Human Resources departments are in charge of managing the incorporation of technology into the workplace. Human Resources officers and leaders need to go outside the boundaries of the ecosystem of work and modify the conventional models of job redundancy and automation. They should also offer ideas like job reinvention, reskilling, and redeployment (Gunathunge & Lakmal, 2021: 123). Automation, together with new practices' flexibility and interoperability, should be the main human resources priorities in Industry 4.0 (Gan & Yusof, 2019: 621). Present-day workers lack of the competencies needed for industry 4.0. However, it is likely that these Industry 4.0 activities will require highly competent, creative, and dynamic people (Vrchota et. al, 2021: 3). Emerging technologies lead to a loss of jobs, a deskilling population, insecurity and growing inequality (Kashni & Singh, 2021: 2).

At this point in Industry 4.0, people are afraid of new technologies. Workers fear they will lose their jobs to digital solutions, mostly physical robots (Kinzel, 2017). Industry 4.0 technology is that organizations lack competent individuals, necessitating staff retraining to adapt to changing conditions (Obermayer et. al., 2022: 1032).

Management

The digital revolution in business is presenting managers with both new opportunities and difficulties. Thanks to new technologies, managers can now techno and retain vast amounts of data (Gaspar & Juliáó, 2021: 60). Through their rapid connectivity and data exchange, all these new technologies and intelligent machines will gather, store, and provide a lot of new data. Choosing what information to transmit, when to deliver it, to whom, and via what media will be critical for management. (Rozkwitalska & Slavik, 2017: 193). Interoperability, virtualization, decentralization, ability to work in real-time, service orientation, modularity and reconfigurability are Industry 4.0 basic six principles (Ungerman and a Dedková, 2019: 3).

Managers in Industry 4.0 processes need to acquire new leadership competencies that align with digital transformation, like the ability to make decisions, solve problems, and analyze data (Tuegeh vd., 2021: 175). It is critical that leaders create plans for assessing the opportunities that arise from foreseeing changes in the Industry 4.0 process and for guiding their enterprises and society into the future (Tetik, 2020: 193).

With industry 4.0 implementations business operations are altered by artificial intelligence that is based on high-speed networks. In the near future big data analysis-based business models will find widespread application. Transparency and new consumer behavior models based on data and mobile network access are produced by digital technology (Genkin et.al, 2020: 5). In management processes, Industry 4.0 adoption necessitates recruitment of qualified personnel, changes routines, and influences planning and decision-making in order to generate high-quality, customized products and services (Ribeiro, 2022: 3).

The use of industry 4.0 technologies in management processes provide efficiency, high financial and market performance and a more competitive environment (Kohnová& Salajová, 2023: 5). In order to carry out Industry 4.0 successfully in management process the following areas have to be considered (Oberer & Erkollar, 2018: 408):

- Standardization
- Managing complex systems
- Comprehensive communication structure
- Safety and security
- Resource efficiency
- Regulatory framework
- Work organization and design
- Training and continuous professional development

In management process Industry 4.0 must be implemented in management processes by reviewing business strategy, investing in all Industry 4.0-related activities, and being prepared to use modern technology and innovative management (Misita & Milanovic, 2019: 427).

Production

Industry 4.0 encompasses data interchange and management in advanced manufacturing engineering systems, computerization of manufacturing, and digitization of manufacturing (Upadhyay et. al., 2023: 1). In industry 4.0 processes, the internet or other network applications, such a block chain, let products and services to be connected flexibly. (Maresova et. al., 2018: 2). The main emphasis of the Industry 4.0 concept

integrates information and communication technologies and attempts to create intelligent production and a smart factory (Zhou ve Le Cardinal, 2019: 2113). Industry 4.0 technologies seek to digitalize all production processes, create new product and process strategies, connect equipment and facilities that can speak with people (IoT), and instantaneously respond to client requests (Cirillo et al., 2018: 22).

Industry 4.0" allow the value chain to shorten lead times for manufacturing while simultaneously enhancing organizational performance and product quality (Salam, 2021: 1699). With the integration of robotic systems and humanoid robots in the production processes of the Industry 4.0 process, the conventional manufacturing factories will be abandoned in favor of new generation production centers known as also "Dark Factories." (Akben and Avşar, 2018: 30).

Using computers, automation systems, and information and communication technologies on the production lines, manufacturing models tailored to individual needs have replaced mass production (Gabaçlı and Uzunöz, 2017: 11). In this processes, companies in the manufacturing sector employ technologies designed to shift from mass production to customized production, (Puterisari, 2022: 103). Adoption of these technologies will allow the machine's production modules to autonomously communicate with and control one another, allowing for the development of more intelligent manufacturing processes (Nagy et al., 2018: 2).

Industry 4.0 processes affect organizational costs. In this context, industry 4.0 might assist a company raise its production rate, but it can also result in higher costs for an organization's technological maintenance (Al Zadjali & Ullah, 2021: 30). Industry 4.0 processes can eliminate demand chain malfunctions and offer benefits like real-time end-to-end visibility for optimal decision making, increased productivity and efficiency of resources, and lower personal costs (Mrugalska and Wyrwicka, 2017: 470). Because of this, industry 4.0 aims to reduce the costs arising from the use of labour force, as well as quality and error-free production with the latest technological production systems offered to enterprises (Akben and Avşar, 2018: 31).

Public Relations and Marketing

Marketing processes also differentiate due to changes and transformations in information technologies (Ertuğrul and Deniz, 2018: 147).

These days, industry 4.0 technologies and artificial intelligence algorithms have made customized items that customers seek more popular (Bayuk and Demir, 2019: 792). Artificial intelligence has the potential to replace a number of mundane public relations activities in the near future. We can make better use of the current technologies available for managing social media and automating different types of content. It is imperative to enhance one's strategic public relations competencies, including analytical and strategic thinking. (Pribadi & Nasution, 2021: 56). Businesses and marketing experts employ a variety of digital technologies in Industry 4.0 to achieve marketing objectives. Digital marketing provides a more effective means of expanding the consumer base and reaching a wider audience by engaging with both existing and future clients (Rosário & Dias, 2022: 4). Value chains are shifting from mass production to customer-tailored products as a result of Industry 4.0. (Kohnová & a Salajová, 2023: 4).

It is interesting that the relevance of e-commerce procedures has increased in the Industry 4.0 process. As a result, companies who want to be highly competitive in the e-commerce sector employ the following tactics (Murdiana and Hajaoui, 2020: 40):

- Market opportunities should be followed,
- Marketing strategies should be developed,

- Customer experiences should be designed,
- Marketing program should be established,
- Customer information should be used via technology,
- Systematic market customers should be created,
- Marketing program should be evaluated.

METHODOLOGY

Objective and Importance of the Study

Industry 4.0 has changed and transformed business activities. Industry 4.0 has paved the way for the change of existing production processes by enabling the application of information technologies to industrial processes. With Industry 4.0, smart production processes have come to the fore. In this new order, it is important to determine the perceptions of employees regarding Industry 4.0. Industry 4.0 has changed the functions of business. In this context, identifying employees' positive and negative thoughts about the concept of Industry 4.0 is important in developing effective business strategies and increasing productivity.

The objective of this study is to determine the Industry 4.0 perceptions of business managers in one of the leading organizations under the building products sector in Turkey. For this purpose, the research questions were formulated as follows:

- 1- What are employees' perceptions of human resources in industry 4.0 activities?
- 2- What are employees' perceptions of management in industry 4.0 activities?
- 3- What are employees' perceptions of production in industry 4.0 activities?
- 4- What are employees' perceptions of public relations and marketing in industry 4.0 activities?

Sample of the Research

This research was conducted by business managers with industry 4.0 awareness in one of the leading companies in the building products sector. In order to do this, participants were interviewed in a semi-structured manner. Thirteen business managers participated in the study.

Data Collection Tool and Data Collection

Semi-structured interview forms were employed in the study as a means of gathering data. All participants were briefed on the purpose and methodology of the study before to the interview, and it was stated that all personal information would be kept private following the interview. During the interviews, data were recorded using the note-taking approach.

Data Analysis

Codes were developed in research. content analysis method was used in research The computer-aided qualitative and mixed data analysis tool MAXQDA Analytics Pro 2022 is used for all aspects of the study's coding and analysis.

FINDINGS

Table 1 displays the participants' personal information.

Table 1. Information on the Participants

Features	Information	Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	1	92
	Male	12	8
Age Range	30-39	7	54
	40+	6	46
Education	Bachelor's Degree	12	92
	Postgraduate Degree	1	8
	6-10 years	3	23
Working period	11-15 years	4	31
	16 + years	6	46

Human Resources

Following opinions are expressed within the human resources dimensions of Industry 4.0 practices: *"Difficulties in finding qualified personnel, prejudiced employees, employment problems, decrease in employee productivity, decrease in labor requirement, preventing employee-related errors"*. Figure 1 shows Human Resources dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Figure 1. Human Resources dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices

Sources: developed by author

Management

Following opinions are expressed within the management dimensions of Industry 4.0 practices: *"Decrease of decision-making processes, difficulties in radical investment decisions, foundations problems, system problems, increase in resource dependency, quick access to information, competitiveness"*. Figure 2 shows Management dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Figure 2. Management dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Sources: developed by author

Production

Following opinions are expressed within the production dimensions of Industry 4.0 practices: *"Standard quality production, flexibility, energy-saving, reduction in costs, increase in productivity, decrease in production process and high investment costs"*. Figure 3 shows production dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Figure 3. Production dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Sources: developed by author

Public Relations and Marketing

Following opinions are expressed within the public relations and marketing dimensions of Industry 4.0 practices: *"Image and reputation, recognition, prestige, error-free production, perception of production quality, rapidity in customer expectations, customer satisfaction and brand recognition"*. Figure 4 shows public relations and marketing dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.

Figure 4. Public relations and marketing dimensions of Industry 4.0 Practices.
Sources: developed by author

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The concept of Industry 4.0 has possible effects not only on production systems but also on business systems such as management, human resources, marketing and public relations. Due to its reflection of the Internet of Things, data integration, informatics, and other technological advancements, as well as its unique qualities that set business technologies apart, Industry 4.0 has acquired prominence in management literature.

Nowadays, enterprises that can survive in these processes will be the ones that can adapt to technological advances. Human resources are undoubtedly the most important production factor of enterprises. In this context, human resources' perception of Industry 4.0 is important for their self-improvement.

This study aimed to determine the Industry 4.0 perceptions of business managers in one of the leading organizations under the building products sector. The study findings supported the previously conducted studies and revealed that Industry 4.0 practices will lead to both positive and negative perceptions by business functions.

In the literature Gunathunge & Lakmal, 2021; Gan & Yusof, 2019; Vrchota et. al, 2021 stated positive aspects of industry 4.0 in human resources dimension while Kashni & Singh, 2021; Kinzel, 2017; Obermayer et al. al., 2022 stated its negative aspects of Industry 4.0 in human resources dimension. Difficulties in finding qualified personnel, prejudiced employees, employment problems, decrease in employee productivity, decrease in labor requirement, preventing employee-related errors are expressed within the human resources dimensions of Industry 4.0 processes. in this research. Among these dimensions, difficulties in finding qualified personnel, prejudiced employees, employment problems, decrease in employee productivity, decrease in labor requirement are expressed negative opinions, while preventing employee-related errors are expressed positive opinion.

In the literature Kohnová& Salajová, 2023 and Misita & Milanovic, 2019 stated positive aspects of industry 4.0 in management dimension. Decrease of decision-making processes, difficulties in radical investment decisions, foundations problems, system problems, increase in resource dependency, quick access to information, competitiveness are expressed within the management dimensions of Industry 4.0 processes. Among these dimensions, quick access to information and competitiveness, decrease of decision-making processes, quick access to information, competitiveness are positive opinions, while difficulties in radical investment decisions, foundations problems, system problems and increase in resource dependency are negative opinions in this research.

In the literature Salam, 2021 Akben and Avşar, 2018 Kayar et al, 2018 stated positive aspects of industry 4.0 while Al Zadjali & Ullah, stated its negative aspects in production dimension Standard quality production, flexibility, energy-saving, reduction in costs, increase in productivity, decrease in production process and high investment costs are expressed within the production dimensions of Industry 4.0 processes. Among these dimensions standard quality production, flexibility, energy-saving, reduction in costs, increase in productivity, decrease in production process are positive opinions while high investment costs are negative opinion in this research.

In the literature Kohnová & a Salajová, 2023; Murdiana and Hajaoi, 2020 stated positive aspects of industry 4.0 while Al Zadjali & Ullah, stated its negative aspects in production dimension Image and reputation, recognition, prestige, error-free production, perception of production quality, rapidly in customer expectations, customer satisfaction and brand recognition are expressed within the public relations and marketing dimensions of Industry 4.0 processes. Among these dimensions, all of them are positive opinions.

The research has shown that employees have positive and negative thoughts about industry 4.0 activities like Industry 4.0 literature. However, it is often emphasized that industry 4.0 processes will bring advantages to businesses. However, it is often emphasized that industry 4.0 processes will bring advantages to businesses in the fields of human resources, management, production, marketing and public relations. Managers should develop the advantageous aspects of industry 4.0 processes and manage the disadvantageous aspects effectively with management approaches. The study in question has contributed to the literature in terms of conducting a situation analysis of the sector. The most important constraint in the research is that the study address only the opinions of business managers of one company on Industry 4.0. In this context, the future studies are recommended to expand the sample by conducting research on different sample groups. This research has limitations. The data obtained from the research is limited to 13 business managers. In addition, the use of only qualitative methods in the research is another limitation of the research.

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